

The Impact of Salary Job Security and Workload on Teachers Satisfaction in Private Schools
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Abstract

This study determined the effect of salary, job security, and workload on teachers' satisfaction in Private Schools in Tehsil Adenzai, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Cluster random sampling technique is applied for selection of representative sample from the population. In order to identify the significant factor influencing the satisfaction level of teachers, logistic regression model is used. The result shows that the salary, job security, and workload have significant impact on job satisfaction level of teachers. It is recommended that private schools should ensure job security to teachers, avoid heavy workload, and should hire trained teachers.

Keywords: salary, job security, workload, job satisfaction, logistic regression model.

1. Introduction

One of the key factors and important assets of human development is education. A large share of budget has spent on education sector globally by government and states to achieve the millennium development goal of education. The purpose of spending on education is to prepare human being to technical revaluation worldwide (Battle & Lewis, 2002). The major goal of education is to increase productivity of human being and to improve their quality of life. Also, skills of students are improved, and they developed new source of earning which finally better for whole mankind (Saxton, 2000). Providing quality education in institution can help to achieve the goals of education. Quality of education improves academic performance of students, which is closely related to job satisfaction of the teachers. Not only job satisfaction is closely related to students' achievement, but it also contributes to the well-being of teachers, overall school cohesion and enhanced status of the teaching profession (Toropova et al., 2021). Society's well-being mostly depends on job satisfaction teachers. Moreover, satisfied teacher would teach to their students with full zeal which leads to better class performance and productivity of schools (Nigama et al., 2018).

Haq and Hasnain (2014) conducted study on job satisfaction of teachers of private school in Bahawalpur. They found salary, workload, supervision, and school climate affecting the jobs satisfaction level of the teachers. Toropova et al. (2021) investigated factors contributing to teacher satisfaction, which are; workload, cooperation, gender, professional developed and more efficacious teachers. Shah and Jumani (2015) found strong relationship between job satisfaction and its indicator (pay) with turnover intention among school teachers. However, they found moderate relationship among job satisfaction and promotion, work itself and supervision. Shabbir and Wei (2015) conducted study on job satisfaction of teachers. They used logistic regression to identify the significant factors associated with job satisfaction. They found that independency and recognition bringing job satisfaction among school teachers.

1.1. Objectives

The present study is conducted in Tehsil Adenzai, District Dir Lower, Pakistan, with following objectives,

- To estimate the proportion of satisfied/unsatisfied teachers in private schools of Tehsil Adenzai.
- Modelling of job satisfaction level of teachers and its associated factors.

2. Methodology

Population of this study comprises all primary school teachers working in private schools in Tehsil Adenzai, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. A sample of 50 teachers consisting of 30 female and 20 male private school teachers are taken randomly from three schools. The schools are selected randomly using cluster random sampling technique. The name of schools is presented by school A, School B, and School C, because the school management is not agreed to disclosed name of their school. Data are collected using structure questionnaires. In order to predict the significant factors for job satisfaction, binary logistic regression model is used.

In this particular study we have a categorical dependent variable which is binary and we cannot use classical linear regression model. In such a situation, we can use binary linear regression model (Agresti, 2002). The response variable is satisfied and unsatisfied teacher, that is, presence or absence of job satisfaction, which is coded as '1' for presence of job satisfaction and '0' for absence of job satisfaction.

For categorical dependent variable Y and an independent variable X, let,

$$\Pi(x) = P(Y = y / X = x) = 1 - P(Y = 0 / X = x),$$

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The logistic regression model is as,

$$\Pi(x) = \frac{\exp(\alpha + \beta x)}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta x)} \quad (1)$$

This can be express as linear ship of log odds and explanatory variables as,

$$\text{Logit} [\Pi(x)] = \log \frac{\Pi(x)}{1 - \Pi(x)} = \beta_0 + \beta x \quad (2)$$

Here β showed the strength of relationship between explanatory variable X and log odd ratio. Its sign shows the nature of relationship i.e either it is positive relationship or negative relationship (Agresti, 2002). Taking anti log both sides of (2) we get,

$$\frac{\Pi(x)}{1 - \Pi(x)} = e^{\alpha + \beta x}$$

Now the intercept term e^{α} is the odd ratio when X equal to zero, and β is slope (Logistic Regression, Lecture notes).

3. Results

Sample of 50 teachers consisting of 30 female and 20 male teachers at private school are selected. Among these teachers, only 10 (20%) are found satisfied from their job.

According to Table 1, 50% of teaching staff of School A is satisfied from their salary while in School B and School C 45% and 32% of teachers satisfied from their salary respectively. Job security is ensuring to 20%, 10%, and 18% of teachers in School A, School B, and School C respectively. Similarly, School A assign heavy workload to teachers 70%, School B assign to 80%, and School C assign to 67%.

Table 1 Teachers Characteristic in Different Schools

Teachers' characteristics	School A	School B	School C
Salary	50%	45%	32%
Job Security	20%	10%	18%
Workload	70%	80%	45%

Table 2 shows the result of binary logistic regression model. Three independent variables are found significantly related to dependent variable. The salary and job security are positively related to job satisfaction level. While, workload to teacher inversely related to dependent variable. Thus, assigning more duties to teachers would result low job satisfaction level of teachers. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.40 represent 40% of variation in dependent variable is explained by the three independent variables.

Table 2 Fitted Parameter Estimates Using Binary Logistic Regression Model

	Coefficient	Standard Error	p- value
Salary	0.584	0.379	0.042
Workload	-0.380	0.118	0.024
Job Security	0.602	0.244	0.002

$R^2 = 0.40$

4. Discussion

The main aspect of job satisfaction of teacher is salary that teacher get as a result of providing their services to school. The study investigated that salary and job satisfaction is positively correlated. Those teachers who have receive higher salary are more satisfied than those who receive low salary. This result is similar to Haq and Hasnain (2014).

Workload is a common reason for dissatisfaction of teacher. It is difficult for teacher to pay attention on their job when they are involved in some extra school activities. Workload also consists of school duties performed outside the classroom. In the present study workload is positively associated with job satisfaction of the teachers. This result is match to Haq and Hasnain (2014).

Most of the private school teachers have no job security. Thus, the management of private schools can dismiss the teachers from job at any time. The fear of dismissal of job lead to stress in mind at all the time, which can affect the performance of teachers. In our study job security is significantly affects job satisfaction. This result is match to Molri (2018).

5. Conclusion

In this study the job satisfaction level of teachers at private school is assessed. The analysis shows that only 20% of the teachers are satisfied from their job. Moreover, salary, job security, and workload are found significantly affecting level of job satisfaction of the teachers. It is recommended that private school management should ensure job security, and low workload to teachers. Further, the management should increase the salary of that they

perform well in school. The present study can be extended to the District Dir Lower by taking more schools in sample.

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